

Brown planthopper biotypes in India

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The differential response of rice varieties to the brown planthopper (BPH) in international screening tests indicated that the BPH population on the Indian subcontinent is not the same as natural populations in other Asian countries. Further studies were conducted to compare the response of rice varieties to BPH populations from southern India and BPH populations maintained at IRRI in the Philippines.

Adult BPH were collected from fields at TNAU, Coimbatore; Tamil Nadu Rice Research Institute, Aduthurai; Agricultural College, Madurai; and Krishi Vigyan Kendra, Pondicherry, to study the biotype variation. Populations were cultured separately on TN1 plants. Pregerminated seeds of rice varieties ARC6650, ARC10550, ASD7, ASD11, Babawee, IET5741, IET6315, Mudgo, Rathu Heenati, Sinna Sivappu, T7, V. P. Samba, and the susceptible check TN1 were sown in standard seedboxes. Ten days after sowing, seedlings were infested with second- and third-instar nymphs and seedboxes were covered with fiberglass mesh cages. Damage was scored using the 0-9

Reaction^a of rice accessions to BPH populations collected from different regions.

Accession	Gene for resistance	Damage rating ^b			
		Population from Tamil Nadu and Pondicherry	Population in the Philippines		
			Biotype 1	Biotype 2	Biotype 3
Mudgo	<i>Bph</i> 1	9 d	1	9	1
ASD7	<i>bph</i> 2	9 d	1	3	9
Rathu Heenati	<i>Bph</i> 3	3 c	1	3	1
Babawee	<i>bph</i> 4	3 c	1	3	1
Sinna Sivappu	Not known	1 a	1	3	1
ARC6650	Not known	1 a	1	3	1
ARC10550	Not known	1 a	9	9	9
ASD11	Not known	3 c	9	9	9
IET5741	Not known	3 c	9	9	9
IET6315	Not known	2 b	9	9	9
T7	Not known	3 c	9	9	9
V. P. Samba	Not known	3 c	9	9	9
TN1	No resistance	9 d	9	9	9

^aBased on the 1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice 0-9 scale. ^bMean of three replications. Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level.

Standard Evaluation System for Rice scale when 90% of the TN1 seedlings died.

Known differential varieties and selected rice accessions reacted similarly to BPH from Tamil Nadu and Pondicherry, but Mudgo and ASD7 rices, carrying *Bph* 1 and *bph* 2 resistance genes, were susceptible to BPH populations from Tamil Nadu and Pondicherry, while Rathu Heenati (*Bph* 3) and Babawee (*bph* 4) were resistant (see table). ARC6650, ARC10550, IET5741, IET6315, T7, ASD11, Sinna Sivappu, and V. P. Samba showed consistently resistant reactions to BPH from Tamil Nadu and Pondicherry. ARC6650, Rathu Heenati, Babawee, and Sinna Sivappu are resistant to BPH bio-

type 1, biotype 2, and biotype 3 in the Philippines but IET5741, IET6315, T7, ASD11, and V. P. Samba are highly susceptible.

Thus the *Bph* 1 and *bph* 2 genes did not confer resistance to the Tamil Nadu and Pondicherry BPH populations; however, *Bph* 3 and *bph* 4 genes conferred resistance to BPH populations occurring in the Philippines and in South India. ARC6650 and Sinna Sivappu also possessed a high level of resistance to the Philippine and the south Indian BPH populations. Those differential varietal reactions indicate that the BPH population in Tamil Nadu and Pondicherry is different from the Southeast Asian population. □

Occurrence of *Porthesia xanthorrhoea* Koller on summer rice

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The hairy caterpillar *Porthesia xanthorrhoea* Koller was first recorded at Raipur on summer rice in Apr 1983. Estimated moth population was 189/ha, with 1:1 sex ratio. Moths were active until Jun. Because no plant damage, except for egg masses on middorsal leaf surfaces, was apparent in the field, laboratory studies were initiated to determine feeding behavior and life cycle.

Oval egg masses measuring 1.2 cm are covered with pale brownish yellow hair, and appear similar to those of *Scirpophaga incertulas* Wlk. An average of 65 larvae hatched from each egg mass after a 6-d incubation.

Newly hatched caterpillars fed on tender leaf sheaths and on cut stems. About 23% first-instar and 43% seventh-instar larvae died in the laboratory. Disease caused seventh-instar death. Pre-oviposition was 2 d, oviposition was 1-2 d, and total life cycle was 47 d.

In the laboratory, larvae were fed whole stems, cut stem pieces, or preflowering, milky, and dough stage spikelets, or a

combination of those. Larvae did not feed on entire stems or milk and dough stage spikelets. But they readily fed on cut stems by tunneling up to 2 to 6 mm. They also fed on preflowering spikelets. They fed on tender leaves (leaving only the midrib) and sometimes on mature leaves. The newly hatched larvae, up to the third instar, fed gregariously on cut stems and central leaf margin, while sixth- and seventh-instar caterpillars devoured the entire top portion of stems.

Larvae fed on the stylet, stigma of the ovary, and anther lobes, but not on the filament. The palea of preflowering spikelets were cut from the middle but the